

Schematic generation of characteristic polynomials and the Hosoya indices of mono- and di-substituted polymer graphs of linear chains and cycles

Piyali Ghosh, Saumya Basu, Somnath Karmakar and Bholanath Mandal*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : piyali1979@gmail.com, saumya.basu@rediffmail.com, skarmakarbu@rediffmail.com, bmandal_05@yahoo.com Fax : 91-342-2567938

Manuscript received online 30 March 2013, accepted 17 June 2013

Abstract : The graphs of polymer chains (such as, chain with two pendant vertices at one end and chain with two pendant vertices at each end) and of cycles (such as, cycle with one pendant vertex and cycle with two adjacent pendant vertices) have been considered. Algorithms have been developed for expressing of matching polynomial (MP) coefficients of such graphs as matrix products and subsequently been utilized to express the CP coefficients (in case of monocycles) and the Hosoya indices of such graphs in matrix product forms. Facile computer programs can be made with these algorithms. Melting points (in Kelvin) and motor octane number (MON) have been found to obey linear relationship with the Hosoya indices whereas the boiling points (in Kelvin) bear a excellent linear relationship with the logarithm of Hosoya indices of two kinds of alkanes represented by the linear chains.

Keywords : Polymer chains and cycles, matching polynomials, characteristic polynomials, Hosoya index, Motor Octane Number (MON).

Introduction

There are large varieties of graph polynomials¹⁻⁴, among them the matching and the characteristic polynomials are of immense importance in physics, chemistry and mathematics. The matching polynomial¹⁻⁶ of a graph of n vertices is the polynomial whose coefficients are the corresponding matching of the graph as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_k (-1)^k m_k^{(n)} x^{n-2k} \\ &= m_0^{(n)} x^n - m_1^{(n)} x^{n-2} \\ & \quad + m_2^{(n)} x^{n-4} - m_3^{(n)} x^{n-6} \\ & \quad + \dots + (-1)^{n/2} m_n^{(n)} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $m_k^{(n)}$ is the number of k -th matching of the graph of n vertices. Number of k -th matching is the number of ways of selection of k mutually independent edges (the edges that are not incident on a common vertex). The concept of matching (acyclic) polynomial was introduced in connection with the topological resonance energy (TRE) of conjugated systems^{2,4,5}. A detailed discussion on the

matching polynomials of paths and cycles can be found in Ref.³.

The characteristic polynomial (CP) of a graph^{1-4,6,7} of n vertices having adjacency matrix A is the polynomial obtained by expanding the determinantal equation, $|xI - A| = 0$, as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_j (-1)^j a_j^{(n)} x^{n-j} \\ &= a_0^{(n)} x^n - a_1^{(n)} x^{n-1} + a_2^{(n)} x^{n-2} - a_3^{(n)} x^{n-3} \\ & \quad + \dots + (-1)^r a_r^{(n)} x^{n-r} + \dots + (-1)^{n/2} a_n^{(n)} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $a_j^{(n)}$ is the j -th characteristic polynomial coefficient of the graph of n vertices. All odd coefficients will be zero except $a_r^{(n)}$ of a graph containing a r -vertex ring.

There are a variety of methods for the construction of CP of graphs. Sachs⁸ showed the computation of CP coefficients as sum over of various subgraphs. Randić⁹ used Young diagram and traces of adjacency matrices of graphs for the determination of CP coefficients. El-Basil¹⁰ presented Lucas sequence and Fibonacci relations to gener-

ate CP coefficients of very large graphs. Mukherjee *et al.*¹¹ developed a method via graph linearisation for construction of CPs of complicated graphs having arbitrary edge and vertex weights. Recently Pascal's triangle like approach¹² with recurrence relations and subsequently a direct approach¹³ to calculate the CP coefficients of reciprocal graphs in terms of number of vertices have been developed.

Though in case of acyclic graph (tree) both the matching polynomial (MP) and characteristic polynomial (CP) coefficients are exactly equal but they differ in case of a cyclic graph. The MP coefficients are used to calculate the CP coefficients of the said graph by taking into account of its cyclic contribution. The MP coefficients have also been used to calculate one of the important topological indices, called Hosoya index¹⁴. Hosoya proposed this index as sum over of all matching polynomial coefficients of a graph and first gave chemical significance of these coefficients to predict physical properties^{4,14-16} of saturated hydrocarbons. Topological indices are used for Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) and Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship (QSPR) studies¹⁷⁻²⁰ that are active areas of chemical research focusing structure dependent chemical behaviour of molecules. Fairly recently Hosoya put forward with proper analysis the chemical meaning of octane number by topological indices²¹ and Balaban *et al.* studied the interrelationships of major topological indices by clustering²². Gutman *et al.* analyzed the Coulson function and established some of its nontrivial relation²³ with the Hosoya index. Two types of topological indices viz. Wiener and Hosoya indices of three classes of reciprocal graphs have recently been expressed in term of number of pendant vertices²⁴. Recently Hosoya²⁵ has presented mathematical meaning and importance of the Hosoya index and proposed an ambitious conjecture connecting algebra and geometry. In the present study we develop algorithms for expressing MP coefficients of two types of polymer chains (chain with two pendant vertices at one end and chain with two pendant vertices at each of two ends) and of two types of monocycles (cycle with one pendant vertex and cycle with two adjacent pendant vertices) in matrix product forms which have subsequently been used to generate the respective CP coefficients and the Hosoya indices of such graphs. The presentation along with the necessary illus-

trations of the algorithms has been given in the ongoing sections.

Matching and characteristic polynomials

Linear chains :

In this section two different types of graphs of linear chains, as shown in Fig. 1, have been considered. The construction of matching polynomial (MP) of a graph (G_L) from the MPs of the two immediately preceding graphs of the same homologous series is well known in the form

$$\alpha(G_L(n);x) = x[\alpha(G_L(n-1);x)] - \alpha(G_L(n-2);x) \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha(G_L(n);x)$ is the matching polynomial of a graph (G_L) of linear chain of n vertices.

The MP coefficients of such graphs of n vertices have also been found to follow the recurrence relation,

$$m_j^{(n)} = m_{j-1}^{(n-2)} + m_j^{(n-1)} \quad (4)$$

where $m_j^{(n)}$ is the j -th MP coefficient of a graph (G_L) of n vertices. Here it is important to note that both the above eqs. (3) and (4) need the MP coefficients of the previous two graphs of the same homologous series. Eqs. (3) and (4) are equally applicable to all graphs of linear chains and cycles.

The CP and the CP coefficients of the linear chains (G_L) can be expressed in terms of the CPs and CP coefficients of the preceding graphs by the equations

$$P(G_L(n);x) = x[P(G_L(n-1);x)] - P(G_L(n-2);x) \quad (5)$$

and

$$a_{2j}^{(n)} = a_{2j-2}^{(n-2)} + a_{2j}^{(n-1)} \quad (6)$$

that are similar to the eqs. (3) and (4) respectively. The relationship that exists among the matching polynomial coefficients (m) and characteristic polynomial coefficients (a) is

$$\begin{aligned} a_{2j}^{(n)} &= m_j^{(n)} \text{ i.e., } a_0^{(n)} = m_0^{(n)}, \\ a_2^{(n)} &= m_1^{(n)}, a_4^{(n)} = m_2^{(n)}, \dots \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The eqs. (3)–(6) cannot be used to calculate MP or CP coefficients directly for a graph of n vertices. Let $m_j^{(n)}$ be the j -th MP coefficient of the graph of n number of vertices. For any graph by definition we have $m_0^{(n)} = 1$ and $m_1^{(n)} =$ number of edges in the graph. But the other coefficients are not so easy to calculate for larger graphs. To address these difficulties algorithms have been developed for such calculations. For this purpose the different

number of matching for few such graphs in the same series have been calculated and written as a sum over of some natural number involving the number of vertices of the graph first and then searched for the inherent relation that exists among the respective sums in the same coefficient and of the sums of the preceding coefficients. This search unfolds some interesting relationships that are helpful to calculate the respective coefficients of a given graph of that series and is discussed in details below for three different types of linear chains. In the following sub sections we will consider only one particular graph at a time but not two or more graphs so the superscripts on the both the MP and CP coefficients are conveniently dropped.

Linear chain with two pendant vertices at one end :

A graph (G_1) of n vertices of a linear chain with two pendant vertices at one end is shown in Fig. 1(a). Such graphs represent 2-methylene ($n - 1$)-polyene chains or alkane chains with pendant methyl groups. Let m_j be the j -th MP coefficient of such graph of n number of vertices; j can have value from 0 to $(n - 2)/2$ for even n and from 0

to $(n - 1)/2$ for odd n . The values of m_j can be written as

$$m_0 = 1, m_1 = n - 1, m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-4} \quad (8)$$

For

$$j \geq 3, m_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n-2j} X_i^{(j)} S_{n+1-(2j+i)} \quad (9)$$

where S_i is the sum of i natural numbers and

$$X_1^{(j)} = 2 \text{ for all } j \text{ and } X_2^{(3)} = X_3^{(3)} = X_4^{(3)} \dots = 1 \quad (10)$$

The values of all other $X_i^{(j)}$ for $j > 3$ can be calculated from the recurrence relation given in eq. (11),

$$X_i^{(j)} = X_{i-1}^{(j)} + X_i^{(j-1)} \quad (11)$$

The eq. (9) can conveniently be expressed in matrix product form as

$$m_j = \mathbf{X}^{(j)} \mathbf{S}^{(j)T} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^{(j)} = (X_1^{(j)} X_2^{(j)} \dots X_{n-2j}^{(j)})$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(j)} = (S_{n-2j} S_{n-2j-1} \dots S_1)$ are row matrices. Superscript T indicates transpose. The matrix $X_1^{(j)} = (X_1^{(j)} X_2^{(j)} \dots X_{n-2j}^{(j)})$ can be obtained with the help of eqs. (10)–(11) and $\mathbf{S}^{(j)} = (S_{n-2j} S_{n-2j-1} \dots S_1)$ is a matrix with element S_k being the sum of natural numbers from 1 up to k .

Fig. 1. Graphs of linear chains : (a) graphs of linear chains with two pendant vertices on one end ($G_1, G_{11}, G_{12}, G_{13}$) and (b) graphs of linear chain with two pendant vertices on each of the ends ($G_2, G_{21}, G_{22}, G_{23}$).

Calculation of the MP coefficients of one such graph of 14 vertices (G_{11} Fig. 1(a)) has been illustrated below.

$$m_0 = 1$$

$$m_1 = n - 1 = 13$$

$$m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-4} = 10 + S_{10} = 65$$

Now for m_j with $j \geq 3$ we need to calculate $\mathbf{X}^{(j)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(j)}$ first whose product ultimately yields respective m_j as is schematically illustrated below.

$$m_3 = \mathbf{X}^{(3)}(\mathbf{S}^{(3)})^T = (2 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1) (36 \ 28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 156$$

$$m_4 = \mathbf{X}^{(4)}(\mathbf{S}^{(4)})^T = (2 \ 3 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7) (21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 182$$

$$m_5 = \mathbf{X}^{(5)}(\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (2 \ 5 \ 9 \ 14) (10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 91$$

$$m_5 = \mathbf{X}^{(5)}(\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (2 \ 7) (3 \ 1)^T = 13$$

So the corresponding CP coefficients of this graph (G_{11}) will be $a_0 = 1, a_2 = 13, a_4 = 65, a_6 = 156, a_8 = 182, a_{10} = 91$ and $a_{12} = 13$.

The CPs of such graphs of 15 and 16 vertices (G_{12} and G_{13} respectively) have been calculated with this procedure and are given in Table 1.

Linear chain with two pendant vertices at both ends :

Such a graph (G_2) of n vertices of a linear chain with two pendant vertices at both the ends is shown in Fig. 1(b). Such graphs represent 2, $(n - 3)$ -dimethylene $(n - 2)$ polyene chains and/or 2, $(n - 3)$ -dimethyl $(n - 2)$ polyalkane chains. Let m_j is the j -th MP coefficient of such graph of n number of vertices; j can have value from 0 to $(n - 2)/2$ for even n and from 0 to $(n - 1)/2$ for odd n . The values of m_j can be given as

$$m_0 = 1, m_1 = n - 1, m_2 = (n - 5) + S_{n-4} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{For } j \geq 3, m_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n-2j} X_i^{(j)} S_{n+1-(2j+i)} - \sum_{i=1} X_i^{(j)} \quad (14)$$

Table 1. Characteristic polynomials of some graphs of linear chains and cycles

Graph	Number of vertices	Characteristic polynomial
G_{12}	15	$x^{15} - 14x^{13} + 77x^{11} - 210x^9 + 294x^7 - 196x^5 + 49x^3 - 2x$
G_{13}	16	$x^{16} - 15x^{14} + 90x^{12} - 275x^{10} + 450x^8 - 378x^6 + 130x^4 - 15x^2$
G_{21}	13	$x^{13} - 12x^{11} + 53x^9 - 104x^7 + 85x^5 - 20x^3$
G_{23}	15	$x^{15} - 14x^{13} + 76x^{11} - 200x^9 + 259x^7 - 146x^5 + 24x^3$
G_{31}	12	$x^{12} - 12x^{10} + 53x^8 - 105x^6 - 90x^4 + 26x^2 - 2x - 1$
G_{32}	13	$x^{13} - 13x^{11} + 64x^9 - 148x^7 + 161x^5 - 71x^3 + 6x$
G_{41}	12	$x^{12} - 12x^{10} + 52x^8 - 99x^6 - 80x^4 + 24x^2 - 1$
G_{42}	13	$x^{13} - 13x^{11} + 63x^9 - 141x^7 + 146x^5 - 61x^3 - 2x^2 + 7x$

where S_i is the sum of i natural numbers and $X_k^{(j)}$ s can be obtained from the eqs. (10) and (11) as discussed in the preceding section.

The eq. (14) can conveniently be written as a product of two matrices similarly as given in eq. (12)

$$m_j = \mathbf{X}^{(j)} \mathbf{S}'^{(j)T} \quad (15)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^{(j)} = (X_1^{(j)} \ X_2^{(j)} \ \dots \ X_{n-2j}^{(j)})$ and $\mathbf{S}'^{(j)} = (S_{n-2j-1} \ S_{n-2j-2} \ \dots \ S_{1-1})$ are row matrices. Superscript T indicates transpose.

With this procedure the calculation of matching polynomial coefficients of the graph of 14 vertices (G_{22} in Fig. 1(b)) is shown below.

$$m_0 = 1, m_1 = n - 1 = 13$$

$$m_2 = (n - 5) + S_{n-4} = 9 + S_{10} = 64$$

Now for $j \geq 3$ the matrices, $\mathbf{X}^{(j)}$ and $\mathbf{S}'^{(j)}$, and thereby m_j for $j \geq 3$ can be generated schematically as shown below.

$$m_3 = \mathbf{X}^{(3)}(\mathbf{S}^{(3)})^T = (2 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1) \\ (35 \ 27 \ 20 \ 14 \ 9 \ 5 \ 2 \ 0)^T = 147$$

$$m_4 = \mathbf{X}^{(4)}(\mathbf{S}^{(4)})^T = (2 \ 3 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7) \\ (20 \ 14 \ 9 \ 5 \ 2 \ 0)^T = 155$$

$$m_5 = \mathbf{X}^{(5)}(\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (2 \ 5 \ 9 \ 14) \ (9 \ 5 \ 2 \ 0)^T = 61$$

$$m_5 = \mathbf{X}^{(5)}(\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (2 \ 7) \ (2 \ 0)^T = 4$$

So the corresponding CP coefficients of the graph (G_{22}) will be

$$a_0 = 1, a_2 = 13, a_4 = 64, a_6 = 148, a_8 = 156, a_{10} = 61 \text{ and } a_{13} = 4.$$

The CPs of such graphs of linear chains of 13 and 15 vertices (G_{21} and G_{23}) have been calculated with this procedure and are given in Table 1.

Monocyclic graphs :

In this section two different types of graphs of cycles of n vertices e.g. monocycle with one pendant vertex (G_3) and monocycle with two adjacent pendant vertices (G_4), shown in Fig. 2, are considered. The matching polynomials of such graphs can be calculated recursively with the eqs. (3) and (4). The eqs. (5) and (6) are not applicable to such graphs. The recurrence relation to calculate characteristic polynomial (CP) of any graph of these monocycles from the CPs of the two preceding graphs of the same homologous series can be derived and is found to be

$$P(G_C(n);x) = x[P(G_C(n-1);x)] - P(G_C(n-2);x) \\ + x^{n_p} (2x - 4) \quad (16)$$

where $P(G_C(n);x)$ is the characteristic polynomial of a monocyclic graph (G_C) of n vertices shown in Fig. 2. Here n_p is the number of adjacent pendant vertices in the graph and in this case its value may range from 0 to 2.

The derivation of this formula (eq. (16)) can be shown as follows.

For simple monocycle ($G_C(n)$) the CP can be written as

$$P(G_C(n);x) = x[P(G_L(n-1);x)] - 2P(G_L(n-2);x) - 2 \\ = x[P(G_L(n-1);x) - P(G_L(n-3);x) - 2] \\ + x[P(G_1(n-3);x)] \\ + 2x - 2P(G_L(n-2);x) - 2 \\ = xP(G_C(n-1);x) - P(G_L(n-2);x) \\ + P(G_L(n-4);x) + 2 + 2x - 4 \\ = xP(G_C(n-1);x) - P(G_C(n-2);x) + 2x - 4 \quad (17)$$

In case of a monocycle with one pendant vertex (G_3 in Fig. 2(a)) the CP for such graph can be written as

$$P(G_3(n);x) = x[P(G_C(n-1);x) - P(G_L(n-2);x)] \quad (18)$$

With the help of eq. (17), the eq. (18) can be reduced as follows.

$$P(G_3(n);x) = x[xP(G_C(n-2);x) - P(G_C(n-3);x) \\ + 2x - 4] - P(G_L(n-2);x) \\ = xP(G_3(n-1);x) - xP(G_C(n-3);x) \\ + xP(G_L(n-3);x) - P(G_1(n-2);x) \\ + x(2x - 4) \\ = xP(G_3(n-1);x) - P(G_L(n-3);x) \\ + P(G_L(n-4);x) + x(2x - 4) \\ = xP(G_3(n-1);x) - P(G_3(n-2);x) \\ + x(2x - 4) \quad (19)$$

Similarly for the graphs of monocycles (G_4 in Fig. 2(b)) with two adjacent pendant vertices it can be shown that

$$P(G_4(n);x) = xP(G_4(n-1);x) - P(G_4(n-2);x) \\ + x^2(2x - 4) \quad (20)$$

Thus for these three types of graphs the recurrence relation that their CP follows is the eq. (16).

The characteristic polynomial coefficients of such a graph can easily be shown to follow two types of recurrence relations involving the CP coefficients of the two immediate preceding graphs in the given series. The recurrence relations depend on whether the number of vertices (n) is odd or even.

Monocycles with one pendant vertex

For odd n ,

$$a_{2j}^{(n)} = a_{2j-2}^{(n-2)} + a_{2j}^{(n-1)} - 4(-1)^{(n-1)/2} \delta_{(n-1)(2j)} \quad (21)$$

For even n ,

$$a_{2j}^{(n)} = a_{2j-2}^{(n-2)} + a_{2j}^{(n-1)} - 2(-1)^{(n-1)/2} \delta_{(n-2)(2j)}; \\ a_{n-1}^{(n)} = 2 \quad (22)$$

Monocycles with two adjacent pendant vertices

For odd n ,

$$a_{2j}^{(n)} = a_{2j-2}^{(n-2)} + a_{2j}^{(n-1)} - 2(-1)^{(n-1)/2} \delta_{(n-3)(2j)}; \\ a_{n-2}^{(n)} = 2 \quad (23)$$

For even n ,

$$a_{2j}^{(n)} = a_{2j-2}^{(n-2)} + a_{2j}^{(n-1)} + 4(-1)^{(n-1)/2} \delta_{(n-2)(2j)} \quad (24)$$

All these equations cannot be applicable if the CP coeffi-

Fig. 2. Graphs of cycles : (a) monocyclic graphs with one pendant vertex (G_3 , G_{31} , G_{32} , G_{33}) and (b) monocyclic graphs with two adjacent pendant vertices (G_4 , G_{41} , G_{42} , G_{43}).

coefficients of the two immediately preceding graphs of the same series are not known. Thus the calculation of CP coefficients directly in terms of the number of vertices of such a graph is a formidable problem. In order to solve this problem, algorithms have been developed to calculate the matching polynomial coefficients of such graphs, which are then subsequently been used with proper inclusion of the contribution of the ring for the calculation of the CP coefficients. As stated in Linear chains Section regarding the development of the algorithm for the generation of the MP coefficients for trees, here also similar techniques have been used to generate the MP coefficients for these graphs of cycles. This procedure has been discussed in the subsections below for the two types of

such graphs. In the following subsections the superscripts on the both the MP and CP coefficients have conveniently been dropped on account of considering only one particular type of graph instead of two or more at a time.

Monocyclic graphs with one pendant vertex :

An n -vertex monocyclic graph (G_3) with one pendant vertex is shown in Fig. 2(a). This graph is a representation of methylene substituted annulene systems. Let m_j be the j -th matching polynomial coefficient of such graph; j can have value from 0 to $n/2$ for even n and from 0 to $(n - 1)/2$ for odd n . Then m_j can be expressed as

$$m_0 = 1, m_1 = n, m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-3} \quad (25)$$

For $j \geq 3$,

$$m_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1-2j} X_i^{(j)} S_{n+2-(2j+i)} \quad (26)$$

where S_i is the sum of i natural numbers and

$$\begin{aligned} X_1^{(j)} &= 1 \text{ for all } j, X_2^{(3)} = 2 \text{ and} \\ X_3^{(3)} &= X_4^{(3)} = X_5^{(3)} \dots = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

All other $X_i^{(j)}$ s can be calculated with help of eq. (28) given below

$$X_i^{(j)} = X_{i-1}^{(j)} + X^{(j-1)} \quad (28)$$

The eq. (26) can conveniently be expressed in matrix product form similar to eq. (12)

$$m_j = \mathbf{X}^{(j)} \mathbf{S}^{(j)T} \quad (29)$$

where $\mathbf{X}^{(j)} = (X_1^{(j)} X_2^{(j)} \dots X_{n+1-2j}^{(j)})$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(j)} = (S_{n+1-2j} S_{n-2j} \dots S_1)$ are row matrices. Superscript T indicates transpose. The elements of the matrix $\mathbf{X}^{(j)}$ can be obtained with the help of eqs. (27) and (28) whereas the elements of the matrix $\mathbf{S}^{(j)}$ are the sums of natural numbers as discussed in the preceding sections.

Illustration of the procedure for the calculation of the MP coefficients for a 14-vertex graph (G_{33} in Fig. 2(a)) is discussed below.

$$\begin{aligned} m_0 &= 1 \\ m_1 &= n - 1 = 13 \\ m_2 &= (n - 4) + S_{n-3} = 10 + S_{11} = 76 \end{aligned}$$

Now for m_j with $j \geq 3$ we first need to calculate $\mathbf{X}^{(j)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(j)}$ whose product ultimately yields respective m_j as is being discussed schematically below.

$\mathbf{X}^{(3)} = (1 \ 2 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(3)} = (S_5 \ S_3 \ S_7 \ S_6 \ S_3 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(4)} = (1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7 \ 8)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(4)} = (S_7 \ S_6 \ S_5 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(5)} = (1 \ 4 \ 8 \ 13 \ 19)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(5)} = (S_5 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(6)} = (1 \ 5 \ 13)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(6)} = (S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(7)} = (1)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(7)} = (S_1)$

$$\begin{aligned} m_3 &= \mathbf{X}^{(3)} (\mathbf{S}^{(3)})^T = (1 \ 2 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1) \\ &\quad (45 \ 36 \ 28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 201 \\ m_4 &= \mathbf{X}^{(4)} (\mathbf{S}^{(4)})^T = (1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7 \ 8) \\ &\quad (28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 266 \\ m_5 &= \mathbf{X}^{(5)} (\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (1 \ 4 \ 8 \ 13 \ 19) \\ &\quad (15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 161 \end{aligned}$$

$$m_5 = \mathbf{X}^{(5)} (\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (1 \ 5 \ 13) (6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 34$$

$$m_6 = \mathbf{X}^{(6)} (\mathbf{S}^{(6)})^T = (1) (1)^T = 1$$

The CP coefficients of such monocyclic graphs with one pendant vertex can be calculated from the respective MP coefficients by using the following equations.

For odd n ,

$$a_{2j} = m_j - 2(-1)^{(n-1/2)} \delta_{\left(\frac{n-1}{2}\right)j} \quad (30)$$

For even n ,

$$a_{n-1} = 2 \text{ and for all other } j, a_{2j} = m_j \quad (31)$$

For example the CP coefficients of the 14-vertex graph of such cycle with one pendant vertex will be $a_0 = 1, a_2 = 14, a_4 = 76, a_6 = 201, a_8 = 266, a_{10} = 161, a_{12} = 34, a_{14} = 1$ and $a_{13} = 2$. The CPs of such graphs of 12 and 13 vertices (G_{31} and G_{32} respectively in Fig. 2(a)) have been calculated with this procedure and are given in Table 1.

Monocyclic graphs with two adjacent pendant vertices :

An n -vertex monocyclic graph (G_4) with two adjacent pendant vertices is shown in Fig. 2(b). By the words 'two adjacent pendant vertices' it is meant that they are pendant to the two adjacent vertices on the cycle. This graph is a representation of 1,2-dimethylene substituted annulene systems. Let m_j be the j -th matching polynomial coefficient of such graph; j can have value from 0 to $n/2$ for even n and from 0 to $(n - 1)/2$ for odd n . Then m_j can be expressed as,

$$m_0 = 1, m_2 = n, m_2 = (n - 5) + S_{n-3} \quad (32)$$

$$\text{For } j \geq 3, m_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1-2j} X_i^{(j)} S_{n+2-(2j+i)} \quad (33)$$

where S_i is the sum of i natural numbers and

$$\begin{aligned} X_1^{(j)} &= 1 \text{ for all } j, X_2^{(3)} = 1, X_3^{(3)} = 2 \text{ and } X_4^{(3)} = \\ X_5^{(3)} &= X_6^{(3)} \dots = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

All other values of $X_i^{(j)}$ can be obtained from recurrence relation similar to eqs. given in (11) and (28)

$$X_i^{(j)} = X_{i-1}^{(j)} + X^{(j-1)} \quad (35)$$

As discussed in the preceding sections the eq. (33) can also conveniently be expressed in matrix product form

$$m_j = \mathbf{X}''^{(j)} \mathbf{S}^{(j)T} \quad (36)$$

where $\mathbf{X}''^{(j)} = (X_1''^{(j)} X_2''^{(j)} \dots X_{n+1-2j}''^{(j)})$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(j)} =$

$(S_{n+1-2j} S_{n-2j} \dots S_1)$ are the row matrices. Superscript T indicates transpose. The elements of the matrix $\mathbf{X}^{(i)}$ can be obtained with the help of eqs. (34) and (35) whereas the elements of the matrix $\mathbf{S}^{(i)}$ are the sums of natural numbers as discussed in the preceding sections.

Illustration of the procedure for the calculation of the MP coefficients for a 14-vertex graph (G_{43} in Fig. 2(b)) is discussed below.

$$m_0 = 1, m_1 = n - 1 = 13, m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-3} = 10 + S_{11} = 76$$

For evaluating m_j with $j \geq 3$ step by step calculation of the matrix $\mathbf{X}^{(i)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(i)}$ and their respective products (m_j) is illustrated schematically below.

$\mathbf{X}^{(3)} = (1 \ 2 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(3)} = (s_0 \ s_4 \ s_5 \ s_6 \ s_7 \ s_8 \ s_9 \ s_{10} \ s_{11})$
$\mathbf{X}^{(4)} = (1 \ 2 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7 \ 8)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(4)} = (s_1 \ s_2 \ s_3 \ s_4 \ s_5 \ s_6 \ s_7 \ s_8 \ s_9)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(5)} = (1 \ 3 \ 7 \ 12 \ 18)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(5)} = (s_1 \ s_4 \ s_5 \ s_6 \ s_7 \ s_8 \ s_9)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(6)} = (1 \ 4 \ 11)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(6)} = (s_1 \ s_2 \ s_3)$
$\mathbf{X}^{(7)} = (1)$	$\mathbf{S}^{(7)} = (s_1)$

$$m_3 = \mathbf{X}^{(3)}(\mathbf{S}^{(3)})^T = (1 \ 1 \ 2 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \ 1) (45 \ 36 \ 28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 193$$

$$m_4 = \mathbf{X}^{(4)}(\mathbf{S}^{(4)})^T = (1 \ 2 \ 4 \ 5 \ 6 \ 7 \ 8) (28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 245$$

$$m_5 = \mathbf{X}^{(5)}(\mathbf{S}^{(5)})^T = (1 \ 3 \ 7 \ 12 \ 18) (15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 141$$

$$m_6 = \mathbf{X}^{(6)}(\mathbf{S}^{(6)})^T = (1 \ 4 \ 11)(6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 29$$

$$m_7 = \mathbf{X}^{(7)}(\mathbf{S}^{(7)})^T = (1)(1)^T = 1$$

The CP coefficients of such graphs of cycles with two pendant vertices can be calculated from the respective MP coefficients by using the following equations.

For odd n ,

$$a_{n-2} = 2 \text{ and for all other } j, a_{2j} = m_j \quad (37)$$

For even n ,

$$a_{2j} = m_j - 2(-1)^{(n-2)} \delta \left(\frac{n-2}{2} \right)_j \quad (38)$$

For example the CP coefficients of such 14-vertex graph of cycle with two pendant vertices will be $a_0 = 1, a_2 = 14, a_4 = 75, a_6 = 193, a_8 = 245, a_{10} = 141, a_{12} = 27, a_{14} = 1$. The CPs of such graphs of 12 and 13 vertices

(G_{41} and G_{42} respectively in Fig. 2(b)) have been calculated with this procedure and are given in Table 1.

Hosoya indices

The Hosoya index (Z) is defined¹⁴ as,

$$Z = Z(G) = \sum_{j=0}^{N/2} m_j \quad (39)$$

where m_j is the j -th matching polynomial coefficient or the number of j -matchings of graph G . It is probably the first topological index that has been used to give chemical significance of certain combinatorial properties of molecular graphs of saturated hydrocarbons. This index for any graph under consideration can be obtained by using recurrence relations. For an n vertex linear chain j -th matching polynomial coefficient ($m_j^{(n)}$) can be written as, $m_j^{(n)} = m_{j-1}^{(n-2)} + m_j^{(n-1)}$, thus for linear chains Z can be obtained by summing $m_j^{(n)} = m_{j-1}^{(n-2)} + m_j^{(n-1)}$ from $j = 0$ to $N/2$, where $N = (n+1)$ for odd n and $N = (n+2)$ for even n , as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n &= \sum_{j=0}^{N/2} m_j^{(n)} = \sum_{j=0}^{N/2} \left(m_{j-1}^{(n-2)} + m_j^{(n-1)} \right) \\ &= Z_{n-2} + Z_{n-1} \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

The eq. (40) can be shown to be applicable for cyclic systems considered here. The eq. (40) is nothing else but the Fibonacci relation that was proposed earlier by Hosoya^{14,25} for path and monocycle graphs. The above equation requires the values of Z for the immediately preceding two graphs of the same class. Another way of calculation of the value of Z in terms of number of vertices can be accomplished by calculating the MP coefficients of a graph with the use of the respective algorithms followed by summing over all the coefficients of that graph. The algorithm for direct calculation of Z for such graphs can be obtained in a compact form from the algorithms for the MP coefficients of the concerned graphs as follows. The Hosoya index of any such graph of n number of vertices is the sum over of all MP coefficients as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n &= \sum_{j=0}^{N/2} m_j = m_0 + m_1 + m_2 + \sum_{j=3}^{N/2} m_j \\ &= Z_n + \sum_{j=3}^{N/2} m_j \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

where N is function of the number of vertices (n). The values that it takes are given in the respective algorithms for the calculation of the MP coefficients in terms of n . Introducing the value of m_j for $j \geq 3$

$$m_j = \sum_{i=1}^{n'-2j} X_i^{(j)} S_{n'+1-(2j+i)} = \mathbf{X}^{(j)} \mathbf{S}^{(j)} \quad (42)$$

where $n'=n$ for linear chains and $n'=n+1$ for monocyclic systems. The eq. (42) is a general form of the eqs. (12), (15), (29) and (36).

Introducing eq. (42) in eq. (41) we have

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n &= Z'_n + \sum_{j=3}^{N/2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{n'-2j} X_i^{(j)} S_{n'+1-2j-i} \right] \\ &= Z'_n + \sum_{j=1}^{n'-6} X_i^{(3)} S_{n'-5-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n'-8} X_i^{(4)} S_{n'-7-i} \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{n'-10} X_i^{(5)} S_{n'-9-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{n'-12} X_i^{(6)} S_{n'-11-i} + \dots \\ &= Z'_n + (X_1^{(3)} S_{n-5} + X_2^{(3)} S_{n-6} + X_3^{(3)} S_{n-7} + \dots) \\ &\quad + (X_1^{(4)} S_{n-7} + X_2^{(4)} S_{n-8} + \\ &\quad X_3^{(4)} S_{n-9} + \dots) + (X_1^{(5)} S_{n-9} + X_2^{(5)} S_{n-10} + \\ &\quad + X_3^{(5)} S_{n-11} + \dots) + \dots \\ &= Z'_n + X_1^{(3)} S_{n-5} + X_2^{(3)} S_{n-6} + (X_3^{(3)} + X_1^{(4)}) S_{n-7} \\ &\quad + (X_4^{(3)} + X_2^{(4)}) S_{n-8} + (X_5^{(3)} + X_3^{(4)} \\ &\quad + X_1^{(5)}) S_{n-9} + (X_6^{(3)} + X_4^{(4)} + X_2^{(5)}) S_{n-10} + \dots \\ &= Z'_n + H_1 S_{n-5} + H_2 S_{n-6} + H_3 S_{n-7} \\ &\quad + H_4 S_{n-8} + H_5 S_{n-9} + \dots \\ &= Z'_n + \sum_{f=1}^{n-5} H_f S_{n-4-f} = Z'_n + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^T \quad (43) \end{aligned}$$

where both \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{S} are the row matrices and superscript T on \mathbf{S} indicates transpose. From the eq. (43) we can find that

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= X_1^{(3)}, H_2 = X_2^{(3)}, \\ H_3 &= X_3^{(3)} + X_1^{(4)}, \\ H_4 &= X_4^{(3)} + X_2^{(4)}, \dots \quad (44) \end{aligned}$$

Combining eqs. (11) and (44) it can be shown in general

that beyond H_3 , all other H_f 's are related by the following recurrence relation

$$H_f = H_{f-1} + H_{f-2} \quad (45)$$

Now let us find how the eqs. (43)-(45) can be used to calculate the Hosoya indices for each type of graphs of linear chains and cycles.

Linear chains :

Linear chains with two pendant vertices at one end :

For such graphs $m_0 = 1$, $m_1 = n - 1$ and $m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-4}$. Thus the Hosoya index ($Z_n(G_1)$) for such a graph of n vertices can be expressed with the help of eq. (43) as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n(G_1) &= Z'_n(G_1) + \sum_{f=1}^{n-5} H_f S_{n-4-f} \\ &= 2n - 4 + S_{n-4} + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^T \quad (46) \end{aligned}$$

Using eqs. (10) and (44) it can be shown that for this case

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= X_1^{(3)} = 2, H_2 = X_2^{(3)} = 1, \\ H_3 &= X_3^{(3)} + X_1^{(4)} = H_1 + H_2 = 3 \quad (47) \end{aligned}$$

and the values of other H_f follow the recurrence relation given in eq. (45).

A sample calculation of Hosoya index of such a graph (G_{11}) of 14 vertices is shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} Z'_n(G_{11}) &= 24 + S_{10} \\ \mathbf{H} &= (2 \ 1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 7 \ 11 \ 18 \ 29) \text{ and} \\ \mathbf{S} &= (S_8 \ S_7 \ S_6 \ S_5 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1) \\ \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^T &= (2 \ 1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 7 \ 11 \ 18 \ 29) \\ &\quad (36 \ 28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 442 \end{aligned}$$

$$Z_{14}(G_{11}) = Z'_n(G_2) + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^T = 79 + 442 = 521$$

Linear chains with two pendant vertices each at both ends :

The expression of the Hosoya index, ($Z_n(G_2)$), for such graphs can be obtained by substituting $m_0 = 1$, $m_1 = n - 1$ and $m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-4}$ in eq. (43) as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n(G_2) &= Z'_n(G_2) + \sum_{f=1}^{n-6} H_f (S_{n-4-f} - 1) \\ &= 2n - 5 + S_{n-4} + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{S}^T \quad (48) \end{aligned}$$

With the help of eqs. (10), (11) and (44) it can be shown that the eq. (47) is equally applicable for the calculation

of H_f . The calculation of the Hosoya index of such graph (G_{22}) of 14 vertices is shown below.

$$Z'_{14}(G_{22}) = 2n - 5 + S_{n-4} = 23 + S_{10} = 78$$

$$\mathbf{H} = (2 \ 1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 7 \ 11 \ 18 \ 29) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathbf{S} = (S_8 \ S_7 \ S_6 \ S_5 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$$

$$\mathbf{HS}^T = (2 \ 1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 7 \ 11 \ 18 \ 29)(35 \ 27 \ 20 \ 14 \ 9 \ 5 \ 2 \ 0)^T = 367$$

$$Z_{14}(G_{22}) = Z'_{14}(G_{22}) + \mathbf{HS}^T = 78 + 367 = 445$$

Boiling points (BP), melting points (MP) and Motor Octane Numbers (MON) of the 2-methyl ($n+1$)-alkanes and 2-, ($n+1$)-dimethyl ($n+2$)-alkanes :

Hosoya indices of 2-methyl ($n+1$)-alkanes and 2- and ($n+1$)-dimethyl ($n+2$)-alkanes with $n = 2$ to 7 have been calculated and are given in Table 2. The data of boiling points, melting points and motor octane numbers of the said alkanes are taken from Refs.^{26,27} and are given in Table 2.

the Z are given below.

$$(MP)_I = (1.9594 \pm 0.235) \times (Z) + (104.984 \pm 5.7231); \text{corr. coeff.} = 0.972$$

$$(MP)_{II} = (0.8996 \pm 0.6227) \times (Z) + (142.4386 \pm 15.7232); \text{corr. coeff.} = 0.715$$

Motor Octane Number (MON) vs Z plot for above two kind of alkanes :

It is a number that represents the ability of gasoline to resist knocking under severe operating conditions. MON is a better measure of how a fuel behaves under load (such as high RPM racing applications). The higher the MON number, the less prone the fuel is to knocking. It has been thoroughly studied by many authors on different occasions with different descriptors²⁶⁻²⁹. Xu *et al.* studied this number with quantum theoretically based descrip-

Table 2. Boiling Points (BP), Melting Points (MP) and Motor Octane Numbers (MON) of the 2-methyl ($n+1$)-alkanes and 2-, ($n+1$)-dimethyl ($n+2$)-alkanes along with respective log (Z) values

n	2-Methyl ($n+1$)-alkanes					2-, ($n+1$)-Dimethyl ($n+2$)-alkanes				
	Z	$\log(Z)$	BP (in Kelvin)	MP (in Kelvin)	MON	Z	$\log(Z)$	BP (in Kelvin)	MP (in Kelvin)	MON
2	4	0.6021	261.42	113.25	97.6	10	1	331.14	144.61	94.4
3	7	0.8451	301	113.55	90.3	15	1.1761	353.65	153.91	83.5
4	11	1.0414	333.42	119.48	73.5	25	1.3979	382.25	181.95	55.7
5	18	1.2553	363.2	154.05	46.4	40	1.6021	408.36	170.25	-
6	29	1.4624	390.8	164.11	23.8	-	-	-	-	-
7	47	1.6721	416.41	192.75	-	-	-	-	-	-

Boiling point (in Kelvin) vs $\log(Z)$ plot for above two kinds of alkanes :

The boiling points bear excellent linear relation with logarithm of Hosoya indices for the two kinds of alkanes as shown in Fig. 3. The linear equations that are obeyed by the plots are given for two kinds of alkanes respectively along with their correlation coefficients.

$$(BP)_I = (144.9615 \pm 4.4305) \times \log(Z) + (178.1912 \pm 5.3263); \text{corr. coeff.} = 0.998$$

$$(BP)_{II} = (128.3338 \pm 0.1591) \times \log(Z) + (202.7828 \pm 0.2091); \text{corr. coeff.} = 1.0$$

Melting point (in Kelvin) vs Z plot for above two kind of alkanes :

Melting points vs Z plot is linear for such graph as shown in Fig. 4. The equations that relate the MP with

Fig. 3. Plots of boiling points (in Kelvin) vs $\log(Z)$ for two kinds of alkanes.

Fig. 4. Plots of melting points (in Kelvin) vs Z for two kinds of alkanes.

Fig. 5. Plots of Motor Octane Number (MON) vs Z for two kinds of alkanes.

tors and found rather a good correlation between MON values of heptane and of octane isomers separately with their quantum theoretically based indices³⁰.

$$(MON)_I = (-3.0584 \pm 0.2579) \times Z + (108.5256 \pm 4.2386); \text{corr. coeff.} = 0.99$$

$$(MON)_{II} = (-2.6086 \pm 0.1485) \times Z + (121.3429 \pm 2.6419); \text{corr. coeff.} = 0.998$$

Monocyclic graphs :

Monocyclic graphs with one pendant vertex :

Introducing $m_0 = 1$, $m_1 = n$ and $m_2 = (n - 4) + S_{n-3}$ for such graphs the expression of the Hosoya index given in eq. (43) will be reduced to

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n(G_3) &= Z_n(G_3) + \sum_{f=1}^{n-5} H_f S_{n-4-f} \\ &= 2n - 3 + S_{n-3} + \mathbf{HS}^T \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The values of up to $H_f = 3$, can be obtained from eqs. (27), (28) and (44) as

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= X_1^{(3)} = 1, \\ H_2 &= X_2^{(3)} = 2, \\ H_3 &= X_3^{(3)} + X_1^{(4)} = 2 \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

and the other values of H_f can be calculated with the help of eq. (45). The illustration of the calculation of the Hosoya index of such graph (G_{33}) of 14 vertices is given below.

$$Z_n(G_{33}) = 2n - 3 + S_{n-3} = 25 + S_{11} = 91$$

$$\mathbf{H} = (1 \ 2 \ 4 \ 6 \ 10 \ 16 \ 26 \ 42 \ 68)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = (S_9 \ S_8 \ S_7 \ S_6 \ S_5 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$$

$$\mathbf{HS}^T = (1 \ 2 \ 2 \ 4 \ 6 \ 10 \ 16 \ 26 \ 42)$$

$$(45 \ 36 \ 28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 663$$

$$Z_{14}(G_{33}) = Z_n(G_{33}) + \mathbf{HS}^T = 91 + 663 = 754$$

Monocyclic graphs with two adjacent pendant vertices :

Taking the values of first three MP coefficients of such graphs as $m_0 = 1$, $m_1 = n$ and $m_2 = (n - 5) + S_{n-3}$ and using eq. (42) the Hosoya index for such graphs can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_n(G_4) &= Z_n(G_4) + \sum_{f=1}^{n-5} H_f S_{n-4-f} \\ &= 2(n - 2) + S_{n-3} + \mathbf{HS}^T \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

Here the first three H_f values can be obtained from eqs. (34), (35) and (44) as

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= X_1^{(3)} = 1, \\ H_2 &= X_2^{(3)} = 1, \\ H_3 &= X_3^{(3)} + X_1^{(4)} = 3 \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

and all other values of H_f can be obtained from the recurrence relation given in eq. (45). With the help of eqs. (51) and (52), the calculation of the Hosoya index for such a graph (G_{43}) of 14 vertices is illustrated below.

$$Z'_{14}(G_{43}) = 2(n-2) + S_{n-3} = 24 + S_{11} = 90$$

$$\mathbf{H} = (1 \ 1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 7 \ 11 \ 18 \ 29 \ 47)$$

$$\mathbf{S} = (S_9 \ S_8 \ S_7 \ S_6 \ S_5 \ S_4 \ S_3 \ S_2 \ S_1)$$

$$\mathbf{HS}^T = (1 \ 1 \ 3 \ 4 \ 7 \ 11 \ 18 \ 29 \ 47)$$

$$(45 \ 36 \ 28 \ 21 \ 15 \ 10 \ 6 \ 3 \ 1)^T = 706$$

$$Z_{14}(G_{43}) = Z'_{14}(G_{43}) + \mathbf{HS}^T = 90 + 706 = 796$$

Conclusion

Graphs under the heading of linear chains represent linear polyene (i.e., polyacetylene) chains. Simple linear chains with even number of vertices are linear polyene molecules and with odd number of vertices are radicals and/or ions. The graphs of linear chains with two pendant vertices at one terminal end and with two pendant vertices at each ends are 2-methylene ($n-1$)-polyene (or 2-methyl ($n-1$)-polyalkane) and 2, ($n-3$)-dimethylene ($n-2$)-polyene (or 2, ($n-3$)-dimethyl ($n-2$)-polyalkane) molecules. For odd n , former molecules are mono-radicals whereas the later are tri-radicals but for even n , both the linear chains represent diradicals. The graphs of simple monocycles are the annulenes and/or cyclo-polyane. The monocyclic graphs with one pendant vertex represent methylene substituted annulenes and/or methyl substituted cyclo-polyane. Pentafulvene and heptafulvene molecules and their alkane analogs such as methyl cyclopentane and methyl cyclohexane belong to this class. There are many other molecules that correspond to this class of graphs. The monocyclic graphs with two adjacent pendant vertices may represent 1,2-dimethylene substituted annulenes (or 1,2-dimethyl substituted cyclo-polyane). Thus the graphs discussed here are not all hypothetical. The algorithms developed here are much convenient to calculate the matching and the characteristic polynomials of such graphs; algorithms do not require the MP or CP of the immediately preceding graphs of the same series. The algorithms developed for calculation of the Hosoya indices in terms of the number of vertices can easily be applied for such graphs. The applications^{4,14-16,23,25} of the Hosoya indices are well known. Motor octane number (MON) and the melting points of few alkanes represented by such graphs bear excellent linear relationships with the Hosoya indices of the two classes of graphs discussed in this study but the boiling points are found to be linearly related to the logarithms of the Hosoya indices of such graphs. The

characteristic polynomials have many important applications. Utilising the CP of graphs several investigators have obtained many important results^{2-7,31} about total π -electron energy with the help of the famous Coulson function^{23,32} and predicted many properties of polycyclic aromatic compounds³³⁻³⁶. It can be shown (Table 5) that the graphs of linear chains such as G_1 for odd n and G_2 and G_3 for all n have zero eigenvalues in their eigenspectrum. The presence of zero eigenvalue in the eigenspectrum of a graph indicates the existence of a conduction band. Thus such graphs with infinite n possess conduction band adjacent to its valence band and are predicted to be organic conductor^{33,37}. Similar conclusion can be made for the graphs G_3 and G_4 . Characteristic polynomials of the sub-units have recently been used to calculate opacity polynomials of composite systems, vanishing of which dictates the zero conductance at a given energy for tight-binding source and sink potential (SSP) model of transmission in single molecule π -conjugated conductor^{38,39}. Fowler *et al.*⁴⁰ provided an analysis of matching polynomial for the interpretation of the topological resonance energy (TRE) of chemical graphs. Very recently⁴¹ algorithm for the calculation of CPs of graphs of linear chains with alternant edge weights have been developed and thereby applied to calculate the CPs of linear poly (p -phenylene) molecules. The sum of the CP coefficients have been found to be a good descriptor for modeling of ambient condition densities and bulk modulus of linear poly (p -phenylene) molecules. Moreover the CP coefficients can be used to generate graph eigenvalues and these eigenvalues have been found to be important in molecular vibration analysis^{42,43}.

Acknowledgement

Authors thank the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, for providing financial assistance extended through the CAS Project in the Department of Chemistry of the University of Burdwan.

References

1. F. Harary, "Graph Theory", Addison Wesley, Reading, MA, 1979.
2. N. Trinajstić, "Chemical Graph Theory", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1992.
3. C. D. Godsil, "Algebraic Combinatorics", Chapman and Hall, New York, 1993.
4. I. Gutman and O. E. Polansky, "Mathematical Concepts in

- Organic Chemistry", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1986.
5. I. Gutman, M. Milun and N. Trinajstić, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1692.
 6. N. Trinajstić, *Int. J. Quantum Chem. Quantum Chem. Sympo.*, 1977, **12**, 469.
 7. A. Graovac, I. Gutman, N. Trinajstić and T. Živcović, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1972, **26**, 67.
 8. H. Sachs, *Publ. Math. Debrecen*, 1964, **11**, 119.
 9. M. Randić, *J. Math. Chem.*, 1987, **1**, 145.
 10. S. El-Basil, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **65**, 191, 199.
 11. K. Datta and A. K. Mukherjee, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1997, **65**, 199.
 12. B. Mandal, K. Datta, A. K. Mukherjee and M. Banerjee, *Mol. Phys.*, 1999, **96**, 1609.
 13. B. Mandal, M. Banerjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 2005, **101**, 119.
 14. H. Hosoya, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, **44**, 2332.
 15. H. Hosoya, K. Kawasaki and K. Mizutani, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1972, **45**, 3415.
 16. H. Narumi and H. Hosoya, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1980, **53**, 1228.
 17. A. T. Balaban (eds.), "Topological Indices and Related Descriptors in QSAR and QSPR", Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, The Netherlands, 1999.
 18. A. T. Balaban, I. Motoc, D. Bonchev and O. Makenyan, *Topics Curr. Chem.*, 1983, **114**, 21.
 19. M. Randić, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 6609.
 20. M. Randić, *J. Math. Chem.*, 1992, **9**, 97.
 21. H. Hosoya, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 2002, **75**, 433.
 22. S. C. Basak, B. D. Gute and A. T. Balaban, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 2004, **77**, 331.
 23. I. Gutman, D. Vidović and B. Furtula, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2002, **355**, 378.
 24. B. Mandal, M. Banerjee and A. K. Mukherjee, *Mol. Phys.*, 2005, **103**, 2665.
 25. H. Hosoya, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 2007, **80**, 239.
 26. L. Pogliani, *Chem. Rev.*, 2000, **100**, 3827.
 27. D. E. Needham, I.-C. Wei and P. G. Seybold, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 4186.
 28. A. T. Balaban, B. L. Kier and N. Joshi, *Match (Comm. Math. Chem.)*, 1992, **28**, 13.
 29. L. Pogliani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1996, **100**, 18065.
 30. L. Xu, H. W. Wang and Q. Su, *Comput. Chem.*, 1992, **16**, 187, 195.
 31. I. Gutman, A. Nikolić and Ž. Tomović, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2001, **349**, 95.
 32. C. A. Coulson, *Proc. Cambridge Philos. Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 201.
 33. J. R. Dias, "Molecular Orbital Calculations Using Chemical Graph Theory", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1993.
 34. J. V. Knop and N. Trinajstić, *Int. J. Quantum Chem. Quantum Chem. Sympo.*, 1980, **18**, 503.
 35. N. Trinajstić, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1977, **49**, 593.
 36. J. R. Dias, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **68**, 107.
 37. S. Kivelson and O. L. Chapman, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1983, **28**, 7236.
 38. P. W. Fowler, B. T. Pickup, T. Z. Todorov and T. Pisanski, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2009, **130**, 174708.
 39. B. T. Pickup and P. W. Fowler, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2008, **459**, 198.
 40. R. Chauvin, C. Lepetit, P. W. Fowler and J. P. Malrieu, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2010, **12**, 5295.
 41. P. Ghosh and B. Mandal, *J. Math. Chem.*, 2010, **48**, 1069.
 42. D. D. Keepports, *Theoret. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **67**, 491.
 43. T. Lu, A. Tachinaba and T. Yamabe, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 1990, **38**, 559.

